

QO'SHMA GAPLARNING USLUBIY XUSUSIYATLARI**Navro'zova Aziza Jamolovna**

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ANNOTATSIYA: Mazkur maqolada qo'shma gaplarning uslubiy xususiyatlari yoritilgan. Qo'shma gaplar uni tashkil etadigan qismlar orasidagi mazmuniy munosabatlarni ifodalaydi, shu tariqa real olamdagi ikki voqea-hodisa o'rtasidagi aloqadorlikni, xususan, sabab-oqibat, maqsad, shart, to'siqsizlik, payt kabi bir qancha munosabatlarni aks ettiradi. Qo'shma gaplarning mazmuni to'liq va aniq ifodalash ehtiyoji bilan, shuningdek, xima-xil ma'no nozikliklari, uslubiy bo'yoq va tasviriy zaruriyatga qarab qo'llanilishi uning nutq va barcha uslublarda dolzarbligini anglatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: qo'shma gap, badiiy uslub, ilmiy uslub, rasmiy uslub, so'zlashuv uslubi, publististik uslub.

Qo'shma gap qismlari birikishida xilma-xil bog'lovchi vositalar ishtirok etishi yoki ishtrok etmasligi mumkin. Bu bog'lovchi vositalarning ishtrokiga ko'ra tegishli mazmun ifodasida turli farq va o'ziga xosliklar yuzaga keladi, bir-biri bilan ma'nodosh sintaktik birliklar paydo bo'ladi. Bog'lovchili va bog'lovchisiz qo'shma gaplar, avvalo, uslub talabi bilan qo'llaniladi. Masalan, ilmiy nutqda dalillar qiyoslanadi, fikr isbotlanadi. Bu publististik va yuridik uslublar uchun ham xos. Ayiruvchi bog'lovchilar gap mazmuni yoki qo'shimcha ma'noni bayon etishda muhimdir. Masalan,

Goh yelkasida ko'tardi to'lqin,

Goh esa muzdek suv quydi boshimdan

(Erkin Vohidov)

Balki ustoz Oybekdek to'lib,

Yozajaksan yangi bir doston.

Balki Habib Abdullo bo'lib,

Sahrolarda ochajaksan kon

(A.Oripov)

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Bo'lishsizlik-inkor bildirgan gaplar ham bog'lovchili qo'llaniladi. Bunda na bog'lovchisi ham o'z vazifasida, ham bog'lovchi vazifasida keladi: Mening nomimga g'alati bir konvert chiqdi: na familiyasi bor, na ismi va na pochta muhri(Asqad Muxtor).

Qo'shma gap qismlarini bog'lovchi vositalar muhim grammatik va uslubiy vazifa bajaradi. Turli ma'no va uslubiy bo'yoq ifodalashda, sodda gaplarni chegaralashda, ayniqsa, ergash gapning nima maqsadda qo'llanilganligini ko'rsatishda bog'lovchilar muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Bog'lovchisiz qo'shma gaplarning imkoniyatlari bog'lovchili qurilmalarga qaraganda ancha chegaralangan bo'ladi. Bog'lovchisiz shakllangan qurilmalar mazmunan uzviy bog'liq bo'ladi. Ular shunday joylashadiki, bir gap ikkinchisin talab qiladi. Bog'lovchisiz qo'shma gaplar bosh gapi tarkibida ko'rsatish olmoshi bo'lgan qurilmalar shakllanadi:Maqsadim shu: yer yuzida tinchlik bo'lsin. Elda shunday naql bor: qari bilganni pari bilmas kabi. Antonim so'zlar yordamida gap mazmuni aniqlanadi:Yaxshi yeydi oshini-yomon yeydi boshini singari. Ayrim gaplarda bo'laklar takrorlanishi mumkin:

Bunda bulbul kitob o'qiydi

Bunda qurtlar ipak to'qiydi (H.Olimjon).

Umuman,bog'lovchisiz qo'shma gaplarda tasviriylik, bo'yoq, jozibadorlik kuchli bo'ladi. Shu bois yengil o'qiladi.

Ergash gapli qo'shma gaplar ham muhim uslubiy vazifalarni bajaradi. Gap mazmuniga aniqlik kiritadi, to'ldiradi, izohlaydi, ta'kidlaydi va hatto, o'rni bilan tasviriy vosita sifatida qo'llaniladi. Badiiy va publististik nutqda nisbiy olmoshli qurilmalar ko'p uchraydi. Ergash gap shaxs,predmet, o'rin holat orasidagi munosabatni qiyoslash, ularga ma'lum darajada aniqlik kiritish uchun xizmat qiladi: Har kimki vafo qilsa, vafo topqusidir (Bobur).

O'zgalarning fikrini hech o'zgarishsiz ifodalash ko'chirma gap hisoblanadi. Ko'chirma gaplarda ham tugal fikr, his-tuyg'u ifodalanadi. Yozuvchi ba'zan ko'chirma gaplardan uslubiy maqsadlarda: personajlar xarakterini ochishda, ichki va tashqi dunyosini tasvirlashda foydalanadi. Ko'chirma gap muallif gapi bilan birga keladi. Shunda to'ldiruvchi ergash gapga

sinonim bo'ladi. Ko'chirma gapni uslub talabiga binoan turlicha qurish mumkin: "Tilga ixtiyorsiz, elga e'tiborsiz"-degan edi Alisher Navoiy. Alisher Navoiy aytgan edi: "Tilga ixtiyorsiz, elga e'tiborsiz". Alisher Navoiy: "Tilga ixtiyorsiz, elga e'tiborsiz" degan edi. Uslubiy bo'yoq talabi bilan va ta'sirchanlikni oshirish maqsadida ba'zan ta'kidlash, uqtirish, e'tirof etmoq, qayd etmoq, eslatmoq, talab qilmoq, ogohlantirmoq, so'ramoq, yolvormoq, ta'riflash kabi fe'llardan foydalaniladi. Mazmunan bir-biriga yaqin bo'lgan ko'chirma va muallif gaplarni shaklan o'zgartirish va bir gapga keltirish mumkin. Ko'chirma gap o'zlashtirish gapga ma'lum grammatik qonun-qoidalar va uslub talablari asosida aylantiriladi. Yuqoridagilar hisobga olinsa, qo'shma gaplarning qanchalik katta uslubiy imkoniyatlarga ega ekanligi ma'lum bo'ladi.

So'zlashuv uslubida uzun va tarkibi murakkab jummalarni tuzish imkoniyati chegaralangan, bu uslub qo'llaniladigan nutqiy sharoit ham bunga yo'l qo'ymaydi. Shuning uchun so'zlashuv uslubida qo'shma gaplarning, asosan, bog'lovchisiz turi ishlatiladi. Masalan: Akosi, atirgul olmaysizmi?

-Singlim ololmayman: oyim lolalarni yoqtiradilar.

Rasmiy uslubda mazmuni to'liq va aniq ifodalash maqsadida qo'shma gaplarning bog'lovchili turi afzal ko'riladi. Yuridik qonun va hujjatlarda jumlar juda uzun, ba'zan bir fikr yarim betlik gap orqali ifodalanadi. Konstitutsiya o'z tuzulishiga ko'ra bob va bo'limlardan iborat. Demak, har bir bo'limdagi matn bir-biri bilan bog'lanishi, biri ikkinchisini taqozo qilishi lozim. Bunda bog'langan qo'shma gaplar, ba'zan bog'lovchisiz va ergashgan qo'shma gaplarning ayrim turlari shu vazifani bajarishga xizmat qiladi. Chunki bunday qo'shma gaplarda ketma-ket ro'y beradigan, bir vaqtda yuz berishi mumkin bo'lgan, sabab-oqibatli, ziddiyatli voqea-hodisalar ifodalanadi. Masalan: Bir fanga ajratilgan auditoriya soatining 25 foizini va undan ortiq soatini sababsiz qoldirgan talaba ushbu fandan chetlashtirilib, yakuniy nazoratga kiritilmaydi hamda mazkur fan bo'yicha tegishli kreditlarni o'zlashtirmagan hisoblanadi.

Badiiy uslubda xilma-xil ma'no nozikliklari, uslubiy bo'yoq, tasviriy zaruriyatlarga qarab, qo'shma gaplarning har ikkala turi qo'llanilaveradi:

- Hamma yoq jim. Faqat pashsha g'ing'illaydi, bemor inqillaydi; har zamon yaqin yiroqdan gadoy tovushi eshtiladi: "Hey do'st, shaydullo, ba nomi ollo, sadaqa raddi balo, baqavli rasuli xudo..." (Abdullo Qahhor)

- U hech nimani ko'rmaslik uchun yuzini kafti bilan berkitdi-da, stolga engashdi. (O'tkir Hoshimov)

Ilmiy uslubda mazmunni aniq va to'liq ifodalash maqsadida qo'shma gaplarning bog'lovchili turi qo'llaniladi: Parlament senator va deputatlardan tashkil topadi va ular xalq tomonidan saylangan xalq vakilidir.

Publististik uslubda radiodan beriladigan eshittirish va radiocherk uchun asosan, qo'shma gaplar tuzilishi kerak. Teleshoular his-hayajon va so'roq gaplar bo'lishini taqozo etsa, "Zakovat" kabi ko'rsatuvlarda qo'shma gaplar qo'llaniladi. Bu uslubda ma'no jilokorligini ko'rsatish uchun qo'shma gaplarning har ikki turidan foydalanilaveradi:

Hurmatli radiotinglovchilar, to'lqinlar orqali xonadoningizga kirib kelyapmiz hamda siz xushnud etishni maqsad etdik.

Qo'shma gaplar mazmunni to'la-to'kis ifodalash bilan bir qatorda, turli xil uslubiy jilokorliklarni aks ettiradi. Qo'shma gaplarni uslublarda o'rinli qo'llay olish fikr mazmunini aniq anglashga yordam beradi.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris "Devonu lugotit turk" in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in “Tamburlaine the Great” by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel “Between Two Doors”, one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo'lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o'zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o'zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo'lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik”, “og'ir dard”, “yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo'llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY “TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT”. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

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Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

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¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

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²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

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